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dialogue
begin**

WORKING GROUP ENVIRONMENT/ECOLOGY

**SUMMARY OF THE WEBINAR ON NATURE-
BASED SOLUTIONS FOR INTEGRATED
WILDFIRE RISK MANAGEMENT**

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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SUMMARY OF THE WEBINAR ON NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR INTEGRATED WILDFIRE RISK MANAGEMENT

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1. Context and general objective

The overarching objective of [Firelogue](#) is to create a network and a platform for the discussion on the future of European wildfire risk management (WFRM), engaging the entirety of the WFRM community. It focuses on supporting the Innovation Actions (IAs) funded under the same call while simultaneously coordinating the integration of actors and findings into cross-sectoral WFRM recommendations into a roadmap for 2030 and beyond. The project comprises five [working group](#) topics (Environment/Ecology, Civil Protection, Societal, Infrastructures, Insurances), which serve as the structure for the dialogue.

Within [Working Group Environment/Ecology](#), the focus is on understanding ecosystems' responses to changing fire-prone conditions and the influence of cross-sectoral policies on landscape modulation, which are two main pillars of the environmental dimension of WFRM. Novel knowledge and innovative actions should assist managers in adapting and managing fire-resilient landscapes across the EU, considering climate change projections and the expected impacts of land use changes in a collaborative and cost-efficient manner. Nature-based Solutions (NbS), for instance, are emerging as a narrative in the context of wildfires but are already well-established in water and flood management. Their implementation sparks discussions that consider several crucial aspects in building fire-resilient landscapes: financial incentives and trade-offs among ecosystem services, and more.

This webinar aims to explore the opportunities and threats associated with the implementation of NbS in the context of wildfire risk management, considering management and financial aspects.

Organized by WG Environment/Ecology, jointly with [WG Insurance](#), this webinar is part of a the Firelogue webinar series fostering a Fire-dialogue. A first webinar on [Fuel management for wildfire risk reduction and nature conservation](#) was already held on April 25th 2024 and was organized by WG Environment/Ecology jointly with [FoRisk](#) and [Forest Europe](#).

2. Agenda

Wednesday 29 th May	
Time (CEST)	Agenda Item
10:00 - 10:10h	Welcome: <i>Eduard Plana, Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia (CTFC), WG Environment coordinator & Claudia Berchtold, Fraunhofer (FhG), Firelogue coordinator</i> Webinar introduction by moderators <i>Marta Serra, CTFC and Juan Picos, University of Vigo (UVigo)</i>
10:10 - 11:10h	Presentations <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Mainstreaming 'fire-smartness' into the nature-based solutions framework. <i>Adrián Regos, Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia (CTFC), Spain</i>• Nature-based solutions lessons learned from natural hazards, the case of protective forests in Austria. <i>Kilian Heil, Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management, Austria</i>• How can insurance enable nature-based solutions for wildfire? <i>Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Austria</i>• Nature-based solutions for integrated wildfire risk management - an EU climate adaptation policy perspective. <i>Peter Löffler, Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), European Commission (EC)</i>
11:10 - 11:50h	Panel Discussion (open to the audience)
11:50 - 12:00h	Sum-up and closure

3. Speakers and Audience

SPEAKERS

Adrián Regos

He is an ecologist specializing in fire ecology, nature conservation, and environmental management. His research addresses ongoing environmental challenges posed by global change, focusing on interactions between fire regimes, land-use change, and climate warming. Dr. Regos advocates for holistic, proactive, and adaptive management to identify NbS and ensure successful policy implementation. Recognized for his contributions, he received the I3 Certificate of Scientific Excellence in Spain, and the Association for Fire Ecology's 2022 Early Career Award. Currently serving as Associate Editor of journal Fire Ecology, he also serves as Guest Editor for Special Issues on 'Nature-based Solutions to Wildfires'. Dr. Regos emphasizes the need for a cross-scale perspective, enabling local action within global initiatives like the New Green Deal.

Kilian Heil

He is a policy officer for natural hazard management and climate change adaptation. He is an expert for strategic planning matters and technical innovation in the Austrian Service for Torrent and Avalanche Control and his work has a special focus on forest fire management. A main objective of his efforts is the implementation of strategic policy priorities for forest fire prevention at the national level. After working for a regional office of the Austrian Torrent and Avalanche Control Service, he joined the superior directorate at the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management. He holds a bachelor's degree in Technical Physics from the Technical University Vienna, and a master's degree in Alpine Natural Hazards from the University of Applied Life Sciences, Vienna.

JoAnne Linnerooth-Bayer

She focuses on global change with particular interest in the risk of extreme events, nature-based solutions (NBS) for their mitigation, insurance for transferring risk, and participatory processes for inclusive stakeholder engagement. Trained in engineering and economics (Carnegie-Mellon University, University of Maryland), she has over 100 journal publications and consultancy reports, including articles in Nature Climate Change, Science, and PNAS. She is a founding member of the Munich Climate Insurance Initiative as well as the Austrian Climate Research Program. She has served as Lead Author and Review Editor on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Special Report on Managing the Risks of Extreme Events (SREX) and the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report, respectively.

Peter Löffler

He is a Policy Officer in the unit responsible for adaptation and resilience to climate change in the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA). His main responsibilities include climate adaptation in EU forest, biodiversity, nature conservation, and health policies. Earlier in his career, he worked in other services of the Commission (Environment, Research, an Executive Agency), and in European associations for green energy and sustainable urban development. He holds an engineering degree in landscape architecture and environmental planning, as well as a PhD in social science.

PARTICIPANTS

The webinar was open to experts in the field, including practitioners, scientists, and policymakers. It was promoted via social media and targeted invitations to networks and relevant stakeholders. A total of 98 registrations were received. Figure 1 below illustrates the global distribution of registrants, highlighting the wide geographic reach. The graphic displays the number of registrants per country.

Figure 1. Webinar registrants' country representation

4. Summary

PRESENTATIONS

MAINSTREAMING 'FIRE-SMARTNESS' INTO THE NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FRAMEWORK. *Adrián Regos, Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia (CTFC), Spain*

Adrián Regos from the Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia in Spain presented a comprehensive perspective on NbS for wildfires, providing a detailed roadmap for identifying and implementing these solutions to address Extreme Wildfire Events (EWE). He began by discussing the changing fire regime, driven globally by climate change and regionally by factors such as rural abandonment, fuel accumulation, and policies that increase wildfire risk in Europe. The presentation emphasized the importance of sustainable solutions to address societal challenges like EWE, promoting policy synergies that benefit biodiversity. He noted that while the concept of NbS is gaining attention across various sectors, its application to wildfire management remains disconnected from this framework, limiting potential political and financial support. The presented roadmap is based on [IUCN Core principles for successfully implementing and upscaling Nature-based Solutions](#) and focuses on several key criteria (embracing nature conservation norms, implemented alone or in an integrated manner, determined by site-specific natural and cultural contexts, societal benefits and equity, maintaining biological and cultural diversity, landscape scale, addressing trade-offs, integrated into policies). Firstly, NbS should address societal challenges such as EWE, while also recognizing wildfires as part of broader ecosystem functions and social components. Secondly, the scale of implementation should consider local stakeholders' perspectives within the context of broader supranational policies. Thirdly, measures should positively impact biodiversity and ecosystem integrity, such as using prescribed burning to improve habitats. Furthermore, the economic dimension is crucial, requiring inclusive, transparent, and fair processes, including compensations for fire regulation activities. It is important to balance wildfire risk reduction with ecosystem service provision, tailored to specific areas. The approach should be proactive and adaptive, with strategies monitored and adjusted to changing circumstances. Finally, intersectoral collaboration is essential, requiring conciliation across different sectors and policy frameworks, supported by strategic communication. Concluding, a nuanced, multi-criteria approach to NbS for wildfires is advocated, ensuring solutions are sustainable, inclusive, economically viable, and adaptable while promoting biodiversity and ecosystem integrity.

NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS LESSONS LEARNED FROM NATURAL HAZARDS, THE CASE OF PROTECTIVE FORESTS IN AUSTRIA. *Kilian Heil, Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management, Austria*

Kilian Heil from the Austrian government presented lessons learned from natural hazards and protective forests in Austria. He started with highlighting the relative rarity of forest fires in the country (approx. 250 per year), which instead faces significant gravitational hazards like torrents (approx. 12.000 catchment areas) and avalanches (approx. 7.000 catchment areas) due to its alpine terrain. Protective forests in Austria serve as NbS to prevent and mitigate these hazards, especially in

mountainous regions. Their protective function relies on proper management and is often complemented by technical measures and spatial planning. The protective role of these forests pertains to socio-economic interests, safeguarding both forest stands and nearby settlements. This role depends heavily on the health and quality of the tree stands. For example, the condition and position of trees are crucial for avalanche protection. Many of Austria's protective forests are in alpine regions, where they provide critical site and object protection. Disturbances like windthrow can diminish their protective function, highlighting the need for combined NbS and technical measures. It was noted that economically, investing in protective forests is cost-effective. A study found that €1,000 invested in forest conservation could replace €150,000 in technical protection measures. A 2022 [Policy Brief from the Alpine Convention](#) underscores the importance of NbS for reducing natural hazards while benefiting biodiversity, nature, and society. Effective implementation requires ongoing maintenance and safety assessments, with cost-benefit analyses comparing maintenance costs to technical alternatives. For successful NbS implementation, recommendations include developing communication strategies, addressing legislative and administrative barriers, securing funding, and involving stakeholders, especially private landowners. NbS should be integrated early in territorial planning and tailored to local conditions. Austria has dedicated funding for protective forests, particularly for rejuvenation and regeneration, which enjoys strong political support.

HOW CAN INSURANCE ENABLE NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR WILDFIRE? *Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Austria*

JoAnne Linnerooth-Bayer from IIASA, started off her presentation comparing the share of economic losses caused by wildfires and other natural hazards. Historically, wildfires account for the smallest share (3%) but the highest level of insurance coverage (63%), mainly due to standard property insurance policies covering fire damage. However, significant coverage gaps exist in Europe, especially in the Mediterranean, where insurance systems do not explicitly include NbS for wildfire management. NbS for wildfires encompass ecological forest management strategies like forest thinning, grazing, controlled burns, and maintaining mixed forests, alongside conservation practices such as ecological thinning, rewilding, cultural burns, and limiting development. These measures require substantial funding, with UNEP's [State of Finance for Nature](#) report calling for investments to increase to \$384 billion annually by 2025 to meet climate, biodiversity, and land degradation goals. The insurance industry can promote NbS through underwriting and investment activities. Underwriting activities can support NbS through:

- Green activities (consistent with current models): Insuring natural capital, de-risking NbS, and enabling NbS financing.
- Yellow activities (potential but needing adaptation): Incentivizing NbS through premium reductions and declining insurance for high-risk areas to discourage development.
- Red activities (requiring new models): Declining insurance for nature-negative projects.

In investment, philanthropic efforts, investing in NbS, and divesting from nature-negative projects are part of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) investing. Despite increasing recognition of nature's role for insurers' long-term viability, major investors often favour more profitable ventures like renewable energy. Barriers to ESG investments include low revenue streams from public goods and unclear definitions of nature-negative projects. To transition yellow and red activities to green,

ideas include compulsory adoption of EU sustainable finance taxonomy (TNFD) recommendations, differentiated premiums, subsidized reinsurance for states adopting NbS measures, and aligning insurance investment policies with EU biodiversity goals.

NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR INTEGRATED WILDFIRE RISK MANAGEMENT - AN EU CLIMATE ADAPTATION POLICY PERSPECTIVE. *Peter Löffler, Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), European Commission (EC)*

Peter Löffler from DG CLIMA highlighted the European Commission's collaborative efforts to address climate change and adaptation amid record-breaking warmings. Climate change significantly impacts forests and forestry, raising questions about the future role of disasters versus management practices. Key EU policies, such as the European Climate Law, EU Adaptation Strategy, and the recently released [EU Climate Risk Assessment \(EUCRA\)](#), address wildfires and NbS. The EUCRA, Europe's first comprehensive assessment by the European Environment Agency, identifies 36 climate risks across five clusters, emphasizing the interconnected nature of these risks influenced by both climate and non-climate drivers like land use. Wildfires exemplify how this as it can destroy crops, infrastructure, ecosystems, and impact health and tourism. The EUCRA stresses that risks interact and accumulate, requiring faster, smarter, and more systemic adaptation actions involving all of society and government. The European Commission's [communication on managing climate risks](#) promotes improved decision-making, risk ownership, and NbS as preferred adaptation strategies. Under the EU Green Deal, various policies address wildfire risks and NbS in a systemic way, including the EU Adaptation Strategy, EU Forest Strategy, and EU Biodiversity Strategy. Legislative initiatives like the European Climate Law and Nature Restoration Law support these efforts, and funding aims to integrate adaptation measures and NbS into major EU programs. The Climate Resilience Dialogue fosters cooperation with the insurance and banking sectors. Despite a robust EU framework, climate and wildfire risks are often underestimated and insufficiently recognized in financial risk management. Prevention and land management are crucial at the member state level, requiring improved implementation. Many European areas remain inadequately prepared for wildfires. While NbS and wildfire prevention are cost-efficient, they are under-implemented and undervalued in financial terms.

DISCUSSION

The discussion began by exploring the boundaries of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in wildfire risk management, emphasizing the need for these solutions to enhance biodiversity and be socio-economically viable for successful implementation in specific territories. Recent statistics showing up to 40% biodiversity loss in certain fauna groups underscore the urgency of the matter. Management measures must be context- and time-specific, as solutions effective in one area might not work in another. The conversation highlighted the importance of prioritizing the needs of specific landscapes and addressing potential conflicting outcomes. Large-scale and territorial planning that aligns with legislation and considers sector conflicts is vital for coherent policies. This multi-objective problem requires a holistic view of the entire system, and clear, coherent messaging to forest owners is crucial. For example, in Austria, forest owners were previously encouraged to maintain wood debris for

biodiversity. Changing this narrative for fire prevention purposes requires careful communication and stakeholder involvement. In Austria, climate change poses major challenges for forestry, particularly in the management of alpine forests. In practice, however, the overpopulation of deer is also perceived as a problem, which limits forest regeneration and thus represents a very critical factor, alongside climate change, for the creation of future-proof forests. Thus, defining priorities and managing potential conflicts effectively through spatial and temporal planning is essential. Prioritization must be tailored to local circumstances, with different priorities in wildland-urban interfaces (WUI) that include more inhabitants and high-risk assets compared to wilderness areas.

The discussion then addressed the role of co-occurring risk disturbances, such as droughts, which initially increase fire risk but may eventually reduce tree density, allowing more adapted ecosystems to emerge. Analysing these relationships is crucial to determine whether wildfires will reshape landscapes or if proactive forest management can mitigate these extreme events. This issue is particularly complex in the context of climate change, which affects vegetation, fire regimes, and recovery capacity. The need for comprehensive climate risk assessments in climate adaptation policies is emphasized to effectively prioritize and anticipate changes over time. In Europe, managing large forested areas within certain timeframes is often unfeasible, making partial adaptation through climate change or wildfires inevitable. Leveraging past fires to reduce future fire probability is important, though communicating this to the public is challenging. There is a significant gap between wildfire management knowledge and public perception, which needs to be bridged for effective implementation. Interventions should focus on areas where high risk cannot be tolerated. Since not all areas can be managed, prioritization is essential.

Currently, fire suppression remains the primary wildfire management response globally, living with the appearance of more extreme wildfires. This raises the question of whether EU "ecologically managed forests" and specific protective forests for lower-intensity fires could be considered NbS, and whether this approach might increase insurance costs if it fails. Integrated wildfire risk management at the EU level includes closer-to-nature forest management, grazing approaches which address multiple objectives, and prescribed burning. However, these measures cannot be imposed; Member States and local governance must embrace and implement them. Systemic change, education, and tools to help those affected by wildfires are necessary. Involving sectors impacted by wildfire risk is also crucial; for example, the tourism sector in Greece was significantly affected after the fire events in 2023. By fostering collaboration among stakeholders and ensuring local adaptation, the EU can enhance the effectiveness of its wildfire risk management strategies.

A question was raised about the introduction of fire in temperate regions where it does not naturally occur. Given the significant uncertainty surrounding climate risk and forest management, there is a need for diverse, no-regret, or relatively risk-free experimental strategies and solutions. Effective risk assessments can help determine when specific measures are necessary. However, it is crucial to communicate these forest changes clearly to the public, ensuring transparency and fostering understanding and support for these strategies, not only at normative level but also at societal level.

With climate change, the conflict between commercial forest use and biodiversity is diminishing, since many measures that benefit biodiversity often also reduce risk which is commercially beneficial.

However, this only applies to a small proportion of the forested area. The discussion now touches on the role of the private sector and how to engage it proactively in non-commercial forested areas. The World Bank reports that 97% of NbS are funded by public sources, despite their broad benefits, including wildfire risk reduction. Public authorities work for societal interests, while private businesses are motivated by revenue. Engaging businesses is crucial, as demonstrated by interviews with Norwegian municipalities reluctant to invest in NbS due to limited funds. There is interest in NbS and wildfire risk management within the insurance sector, but practical action remains limited. Emerging blended models could address this gap, directing public utilities and tax money towards nature conservation. Public funds for NbS should be invested where cost-benefit analyses show positive outcomes. However, ongoing maintenance of NbS can be costly and challenging to manage, whereas technical measures may be expensive to implement initially but require less restoration over time. A mixed approach, incorporating both NbS and technical measures, can be considered. Another option is to incentivize businesses to participate in risk reduction to limit business losses. For example, in Galicia, Spain, a factory had to halt operations for days while many workers defended their homes against wildfires. In Austria, natural hazard projects help municipalities create safer living spaces. National law mandates that those who receive protection must contribute to the costs, with government and municipalities handling the financial process collaboratively. By fostering collaboration among stakeholders, ensuring local adaptation, and balancing public and private investment, the EU can enhance the effectiveness of its wildfire risk management strategies.

In the implementation of solutions at Member State level, it was pointed out that forest ownership structures vary across Europe, impacting landscape management and wildfire prevention. In Portugal, fragmented ownership and a lack of land register hinder effective management. In contrast, Poland's state-owned forests allow coordinated action. Community involvement in financing and implementing NbS projects enhances success, as seen in Austria's natural hazards projects. Community insurance, similar to flood risk management in the United States of America (USA), could be applied to wildfires, encouraging collective measures and resident pressure on public authorities.

The discussion concluded with an open question on the necessity of an EU Fire Directive, similar to the Flood Directive, or a Climate Risk Directive to promote a multi-hazard approach that considers trade-offs across risk reduction measures and ecosystem services. Given the current context of climate change and the increasing urgency of various climate risks (e.g., floods, tornadoes, hurricanes) and their cascading effects, it was debated whether such directives could raise awareness among policymakers and stakeholders or create competition among agencies for limited resources.

5. Final remarks

The following points summarize the main highlights of the webinar:

- NbS can be combined with technical measures to increase efficiency. There is a need for diverse, low-risk experimental strategies.
- There is a need to better define and agree on the understanding and criteria of NbS applied for WFR reduction.
- NbS offers significant societal benefits that are not easily monetized and are currently funded mainly by public sources. There is a need to involve private businesses mainly motivated by revenue, incentivizing them to reduce wildfire risk. There is a growing interest from the insurance sector but up until now practical action is limited.
- Gaps to be addressed for effective implementation of NbS is the lack of practical and financial tools for implementation, and the fragmented forest ownership structures in some Member States, which impact wildfire prevention and limit large-scale measure implementation.
- Besides achieving their main purpose (e.g. wildfire risk reduction), NbS should aim to achieve multiple objectives, from which most importantly enhancing ecological diversity and being socio-economically viable. Land planning must align with larger-scale legislation while adapting to local conditions. Indeed, priorities should be set based on the specific context of each territory, ensuring that measures are both context- and time-specific.
- Prioritization should also consider specific area characteristics, defining priorities for different landscape types and vulnerable areas such as WUI. High-risk areas should be prioritized for interventions.
- Conflicting outcomes from various objectives and sectoral differences can be managed by setting clear priorities for each territory, incorporating these priorities into risk assessments and cost-benefit analyses.
- Relationships between co-occurring risk disturbances and cascading effects need to be analysed to determine landscape impacts. Comprehensive climate risk assessments are essential.
- Under NbS frame, there is a need to accept partial forest adaptation due to direct effects of climate change or wildfires. Clear communication to the public about forest changes and management strategies is crucial, as is bridging the gap between wildfire management knowledge and public perception.
- Consistent messaging to forest owners is essential, avoiding abrupt narrative shifts. Engaging stakeholders and involving the community in NbS has shown to enhance success. There is potential for community insurance models similar to USA flood risk management.

